

TENSILE PROPERTIES OF CRYSTALLINE POLYMER COMPOSITE SYSTEMS FILLED WITH SPHERICAL SILICA NANOPARTICLES HAVING HYDROPHILIC SURFACES

Mitsuru Tanahashi¹, Mizuki Deguchi¹ and Kosuke Nomura²

¹ Department of Mechanical Systems Engineering, Faculty of Engineering,
Toyama Prefectural University,
5180 Kurokawa, Imizu 939-0398, Japan (tanahashi@pu-toyama.ac.jp)

² Department of Materials Design Innovation Engineering, Graduate School of Engineering,
Nagoya University,
Furo-cho, Chikusa-ku, Nagoya 464-8603, Japan

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ABSTRACT

The tensile properties of crystalline polymer nano-composite systems filled with silica nanospheres having hydrophilic surfaces were investigated with a focus on effects of hydrophilic nature of surfaces of silica nanofillers on their properties. The authors have fabricated the perfluoropolymer and polypropylene nano-composites, wherein isolated colloidal silica primary nanospheres without any surface modification using silane coupling agents could be dispersed through the breakdown of loose agglomerates of their colloidal spheres in each polymer matrix component. Both of these two nano-composite systems have exhibited excellent characteristics in terms of elongation properties caused by a reduction of stress concentration due to the silica/matrix interfacial debonding during a large plastic deformation. It was also found that the ultimate tensile strengths as well as the Young's moduli of both of the two nano-composites increase by filling silica primary nanospheres in an isolated and uniformly dispersed state to the polymer matrix in spite of an incorporation of the silica fillers having little adhesion with polymer matrix. The improvement in the tensile properties observed in this study suggested a possibility of toughening the crystalline polymers such as perfluoropolymer and polypropylene by filling a small amount of silica nanospheres with untreated hydrophilic surfaces.

1 INTRODUCTION

Polymer nano-composites comprise a new class of materials in which nanoscale inorganic particulates are finely dispersed as fillers within the matrices. Their principle features are a large interfacial area between fillers and polymer matrix phase and a short surface distance between neighboring fillers. The polymer nano-composites have been fabricated conventionally utilizing a blending method with an enhancement wettability of nanofillers having hydrophilic surfaces against a hydrophobic polymer matrix via surface modification using silane coupling agents [1], resulting in a formation of boundary layer with a thickness about several to tens of nanometers at the interface between filler and polymer matrix that is also referred to as bound polymer [2]. In the boundary layers, a reduction in polymer chain mobility and an increase in rigidity occur due to affinity of modified filler surface with a molecule of the matrix polymer to exhibit interaction. Since a dimension of the boundary layers thickness is roughly same level as a distance between neighboring fillers in nano-composites, the layers having extensive areas determines the characteristics of the nano-composite. In comparison with neat polymers and microparticulate composites, the nano-composites have been expected to exhibit markedly improved properties, including modulus, strength, heat resistance, and so on. However, for the conventional type of polymer nano-composites designed for use with surface-modified fillers, a rigidity of the boundary layers often causes a deterioration of parts of mechanical characteristics of its neat polymer such as elongation properties and impact resistance [3]. On the other hand, effects of the interface between hydrophobic polymer matrix and originally hydrophilic inorganic nanofillers like surface of hydroxylated silica on the mechanical properties of the polymer nano-composites has not been well understood up to now.

From the viewpoint of this issue, the authors have investigated some mechanical characteristics of the silica/polymer nano-composites, wherein nano-sized spherical silica fillers without any surface modification using silane coupling agents were dispersed uniformly. The aim of the present study is to elucidate the effects of an absence of a rigid boundary layer between dispersed silica and the polymer matrix phases, that is, a poor adhesion of the silica/polymer interfaces on tensile properties of the silica/polymer nano-composite system. For this purpose, two kinds of crystalline polymer, poly(tetrafluoroethylene-*co*-perfluoropropylvinylether) (PFA) and polypropylene (PP) having poor wettability to silica filler were picked up as polymer matrices of nano-composite systems.

2 EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

2.1 Method for fabrication of nano-composites

In general, secondary particles wherein nano-sized silica primary particles aggregate are used as silica fillers for fabrication of silica/polymer nano-composites by the use of a blending method with polymer matrix component. From this viewpoint, the experimental techniques on the basis of the strategy for the pre-control of packing structure of secondary particles consisting of silica primary nanospheres as loosely as possible to enable easy breaking down and achieving almost the entire dispersion into isolated primary spheres at a blending stage with polymeric matrix components was used as the method for fabrication of the silica/PFA and the silica/PP nano-composites [4-6]. This method consists of two stages as illustrated in Figure 1. The first stage involves preparation of secondary particles consisting of colloidal silica primary nanospheres, that is, loose silica agglomerates intended to control their packing structures to a random state with large amounts of void spaces, and the second one involves blending of PFA or PP with the loose silica agglomerates prepared in the first stage. In the first stage, the colloidal silica nanospheres coagulate in an aqueous

Figure 1: Process flow illustration for fabrication of the silica/PFA and silica/PP nano-composites by melt-compounding method combined with process for preparing secondary particles with pre-controlled loose packing structures of colloidal silica nanospheres as fillers that enable acceleration of breakdown their agglomerates and achievement of almost entire dispersion into isolated primary spheres via blending with each PFA or PP polymeric matrix component.

solution of colloidal silica (silica sol solution) with a primary diameter of 200 nm destabilized via pH control to 4 from its initial condition and salt addition using KBr, resulting in formation of random packing structure of colloidal silica primary nanospheres as loosely as possible. Removing salt and evaporating off the water yielded the loose silica agglomerates. In the second stage, PFA and PP were individually blended with prescribed amounts of the prepared silica agglomerates in each of twin-screw kneader. The silica/PFA composites were fabricated using an intensive batch kneader, Labo Plastomill with KF70 type mixer (Toyo Seiki Seisaku-sho, Ltd.). The blending processes for this composite system were operated at 340-370 °C for 1300 s under a condition where screw rotational speed was changed cyclically between a wide range from a high mode (240 rpm) for 20 s to a low one (20 rpm) for 240 s to keep in a high shear blending state. The silica/PP composites were fabricated using a micro compounder, MC 15 (Xplore instruments) at 200 °C for 600 s under a condition of constant screw rotational speed being 200 rpm.

2.2 Tensile tests

Dumbbell-shaped specimens for the tensile test were prepared by an injection molding. Tensile tests were carried out at room temperature using the prepared specimens of the silica/PFA and the silica/PP composite systems, respectively, according to JIS K 7127 using the TENSILON (UTM-1T or SS-207-EP, Toyo Baldwin) instrument with a the cross-head speed of 50 mm/min and according to ASTM D638 using the universal testing machine (Autograph AG-Xplus, Shimadzu) with a the cross-head speed of 10 mm/min.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Dispersibilities of silica in fabricated composite samples

Figure 2 shows a scanning electron microscope (SEM) images of an example of arrangement structures in the agglomerates of colloidal silica primary nanospheres prepared to use as secondary particles of silica fillers for the fabrication of the nano-composites. This figure shows that large amounts of nano-sized void spaces could be generated in the silica agglomerates. It was guessed that the loose agglomerates have random packing structure of colloidal silica primary spheres that enable acceleration of breakdown their agglomerates via blending with each PFA or PP polymeric matrix component.

Figure 2: SEM micrographs showing arrangement structures in the agglomerates of colloidal silica primary nanospheres prepared to use as secondary particles of silica fillers.

The dispersion states of silica in the fabricated the silica/PFA and the silica/PP nano-composites were examined by a transmission electron microscopy (TEM) and a SEM observations. Figure 3 shows examples of distribution of colloidal silica nanospheres in (a) the silica/PFA and (b) the silica/PP composites fabricated, respectively, under the conditions of silica volume fraction, V_f , being 0.028 and 0.021. These micrographs clearly show that isolated primary nanospheres of colloidal silica with originally hydrophilic surfaces could be dispersed uniformly in both composites through breakdown of loose silica agglomerates by a shear force generated in the compounded thermoplastic

polymer melt including a completely hydrophobic perfluoropolymer used as a matrix component. It was found that the proposed experimental techniques of the simple melt-compounding method using the loose silica agglomerates enables a successful fabrication of the silica/polymer nano-composites without any hydrophobic surface modification of silica nanofillers.

Figure 3: SEM micrographs (including partly TEM one) showing examples of distribution of silica primary nanospheres having hydrophilic surfaces in (a) silica/PFA and (b) silica/PP nano-composites fabricated, respectively, using 2.8 vol% and 2.1 vol% loose silica agglomerates as secondary particles of silica fillers. The bright spots in SEM micrographs and the dark spots in TEM micrograph are isolated colloidal silica primary nanospheres dispersed in these composite samples.

3.2 Tensile properties of silica/PFA nano-composite system

As some examples of the results of the tensile tests of the fabricated silica/PFA composite system, typical stress-strain (S-S) curves of this nano-composite with V_f being 0.028 are shown in Figure 4 together with its macro-composite fabricated by incorporation of the same volume fraction of silica fillers as micro-sized aggregations and neat PFA unfilled with silica. The S-S curve of the nano-composite displays a drastic improvement in elongation properties compared to the macro-composite in which a localized large stress concentration causing an unstable fracture occurs around micro-sized aggregations of silica fillers during its tensile test. The comparison of these two S-S curves indicates that a good dispersion of silica nanofillers in composites reduces the stress concentration and enhances the uniformity of stress distribution, resulting in a significant increase in fracture strain. A particularly noteworthy results is that the fracture strain, ε_f , and the maximum stress at the fracture point (ultimate tensile strength, σ_u) of the nano-composite are, respectively, larger than those of the neat PFA.

In the cases of the silica/PFA nano-composites fabricated with the other silica volume fraction, all the S-S curves were provided with their respective maximum values, σ_u , at their fracture points. The

Figure 4: Typical S-S curve of the silica/PFA nano-composite with silica volume fraction of 0.028, compared to its macro-composite with the same silica volume fraction and neat PFA unfilled with silica.

values of σ_u , ϵ_f , and the modulus of toughness, u_t , determined from the S-S curves of the fabricated nano-composites including the neat PFA were plotted in Figure 5 (a)-(c), respectively, against silica volume fraction. The modulus of toughness representing the strain energy per unit volume, that is, strain energy density that a material can absorb just before its fracture calculated as the area under the S-S curve of each nano-composite up to its fracture point. At a small volume fraction of silica of 0.028, a distinct increase in all of the results of σ_u , ϵ_f , and u_t was observed before encountering their decays at higher silica volume fraction. The cause of an improvement in both the tensile properties of strength and toughness observed in this composite system filled with small amounts of hydrophilic silica nanospheres having little adhesion with PFA matrix phase have been considered by comparing the deformation mechanism of these composite systems with that of neat PFA. During a plastic deformation of this nano-composite system, micro-voids are nucleated out of the isolated silica nanospheres dispersed by the application of tensile load. The nucleation of micro-voids enables Poisson's contraction between the voids that can relax the strain constraint causing the stress concentration of the tip of the locally practically deformed zone in the PFA matrix phase. When the micro-voids nucleated at the silica/PFA interfaces are not large enough in number to fracture immediately through their growth and coalescence, this nano-composite system that possess both toughness and ductility can be realized, as indicated by the results of the nano-composite with V_f being 0.028 in Figures 4 and 5. On the other hand, a fracture of neat PFA unfilled with silica fillers inducing micro-void nucleations is triggered by crazing during its plastic deformation. A crazing that is a local deformation phenomenon specific to polymeric materials having heterogeneous microstructures reacts sensitively with a microscopic stress concentration. The neat PFA is, therefore, fractured unstably accompanying its own deformation smaller than the silica/PFA nano-composite system. Since a fracture mode of neat PFA might be more brittle than that of its nano-composite filled with hydrophilic silica at a low volume fraction (*i.e.* $V_f = 0.028$). However, in the case of a higher V_f silica loading than 0.028, the plastic deformation nucleate so many micro-voids that they coalesce more easily, resulting in decrease in fracture strain and ultimate tensile strength and deterioration in toughness, as shown in Figure 5.

3.3 Tensile properties of silica/PP nano-composite system

Figure 6 shows typical examples of the S-S curves obtained from the tensile tests of the fabricated silica/PP composite system with V_f being 0.021. Dissimilarly to the S-S curves of the silica/PFA

Figure 5: Effects of silica volume fraction on (a) ultimate tensile strength, (b) fracture strain, and (c) modulus of toughness of silica/PFA nano-composite system.

Figure 6: Typical S-S curve of the silica/PP nano-composite with silica volume fraction of 0.021, compared to its macro-composite with the same silica volume fraction and neat PP unfilled with silica.

composite system, these curves display a clear yielding behavior at a strain lower than 0.1. It is found from this figure that the Young's modulus of the silica/PP composite system as measured from the initial slope of each enlarged S-S curve in the inset as well as the yield stress increased with decreasing size of the silica fillers dispersed in PP matrix.

The increase in the modulus by filling silica indicates an increase in the rigidity of PP related to the restriction of the mobility in PP matrix due to an incorporation of silica fillers, even though silica fillers have little adhesion with matrix polymer. This is because the tensile stress transferred from the PP matrix to the dispersed silica fillers with high modulus during a small elastic deformation that does not result an interface separation between silica fillers and the polymer matrix. It was found from the inset in Figure 6 that a Young's modulus of the silica/PP composite system fabricated in the preset study was determined not by bonding strength between silica nanofillers and PP matrix but by dispersibility of silica nanospheres.

On the other hand, in both the cases of the nano- and macro-composites filled with silica, the stress showing almost constant value, independent of strain, during a necking deformation after yielding were higher than that in the case of the neat PP unfilled with silica, which suggests the possibility of a toughening PP by filling silica having little adhesion with matrix polymer as observed in the case of the silica/PFA nano-composite system shown in Figures 4 and 5. A necking deformation of crystalline polymer such as PFA and PP used as a matrix component in the present study is explained with the following molecular model. At this deformation stage, a slip-tilting of lamellae is induced once the amorphous ties between the lamellae. As deformation continues, lamellae fragments get aligned in the direction of draw, resulting in the formation of fibrils of alternating crystal blocks and stretched amorphous regions [7]. It is considered from Figure 6 that the dispersed silica fillers might hinder an alignment of lamellae fragments in the PP matrix phase, which leads to an increase in the tensile load required for the deformation expanding the necked region of the composite, in comparison to the necking behavior of the neat PP unfilled with silica.

Finally, a high-strengthening of crystalline PP by filling silica nanospheres with hydrophilic surfaces in an isolated and uniformly dispersed state were examined with a focus on the results of the yeild stress of the silica/PP nano-composite system. The dependence of silica volume fraction on the yeild stress, σ_Y , of this nano-composite system are shown in Figure 7. In this figure, the yeild stress of this composite system predicted by the following equation expressing the Nicolais-Narkis model [8]:

$$\sigma_Y / \sigma_{Y,m} = 1 - 1.21 V_f^{2/3} \quad (1)$$

Figure 7: Effect of silica volume fraction on yield stress of silica/PP nano-composite system. The broken line represents the yield stress predicted on the basis of the Nicolais-Narkis model.

are also plotted to compare with the measured values of σ_Y . The predicted values were calculated from the Nicolais-Narkis equation (Equation (1)) on the assumption of no adhesion between filler and polymer matrix, using the measured values of $\sigma_{Y,m}$ of the neat PP obtained in the present study. The decrease of the predicted yield stress, σ_Y , associated with increase in filler volume fraction, V_f , seems to be caused by no stress transfer from polymer matrix to fillers due to an interfacial debonding between fillers and polymer matrix phase at the yield point of its composite. In general, the yield stress of a ductile polymer is decreased by incorporating filler particles having little adhesion with its polymer phase [9-16], as indicated by the Nicolais-Narkis model [8]. It has been, therefore, recognized that a modification of hydrophilic surfaces of fillers to hydrophobic one that connects strongly between the fillers and matrix polymer is necessary for the increment in yield strength of the composite [12-16]. On the other hand, contrary to the prediction on the basis of the Nicolais-Narkis model [8], an increase in yield stress of the PP nano-composite fabricated in the present study can be observed in Figure 7 by incorporation of hydrophilic silica primary nanospheres having little adhesion with PP matrix phase in an isolated dispersion state. The values of the strain at yield of the neat PP and the composites are not so dissimilar from their elastic limit strain that high tensile stress generated within the elastic deformation range, which corresponds to the high Young's modulus, might lead to the increase in the yield stress regarded as a ultimate tensile strength in the case of this composite system, with filling small amounts of silica. However, at a higher silica volume fraction, an adverse effect of little stress transfer from PP matrix to silica fillers, as described in the Nicolais-Narkis model [8] seems to get actualized to suppress the increase in yield stress.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The effects of little adhesion of silica/matrix interfaces on the tensile properties of ductile crystalline polymer nano-composites were investigated in the silica/PFA and the silica/PP systems. The following results were obtained.

- (i) Practical technique that enables to achieve a uniform dispersion of isolated primary nanospheres of colloidal silica with untreated hydrophilic surfaces into PFA and PP matrices could be developed successfully.
- (ii) As the results on the tensile properties of the silica/PFA composite systems, both the ultimate tensile strength and the toughness increased by filling small amounts of silica primary nanospheres in an isolated and uniformly dispersed state.
- (iii) As the results on the tensile properties of the silica/PP composite systems, the yield stress that was equivalent to the ultimate tensile strength, as well as the Young's modulus, could be improved by filling small amounts of silica nanospheres was strongly affected by dispersibility of silica. The stress generated during a necking deformation after yielding was higher than that in the case of the neat PP. These results suggest a possibility that a toughening PP can be achieved by filling small amounts of hydrophilic silica nanospheres as observed in the case of the silica/PFA nano-composite system.
- (iv) It was found that micro-void formation at the silica fillers/polymer matrix interfaces during a large plastic deformation due to little adhesion between these two phases makes a significant contribution to an improvement in elongation properties of these two composite systems. Within a small deformation range from a load-less initial state to yielding point including an elastic deformation, the stress transfer from the polymer matrix phase to the dispersed silica phases that is indispensable to increase the stiffness and the strength could be occur in spite of little adhesion between these two phases.

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